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A Decision Support System for Air Traffic Definition and Identification

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ABSTRACT

Recent advancements in weapon and platform systems have necessitated the enhancement of surveillance, detection, tracking, and identification capabilities within military command and control (C2) frameworks. The operational success and defensive capacity against sophisticated threats critically depend on the timely and accurate acquisition of sensor data and intelligence. As operational complexities and mission demands escalate, the integration of multi-sensor systems, strategic planning capabilities, and unified C2 infrastructures has emerged as a foundational requirement for informed and timely decision-making, even during non-combat periods. In this context, we propose a robust and integrated decision support system based on a multi-layered, multi-sensor architecture aimed at enhancing the precision of aircraft classification and identification. The system comprises two distinct layers. The lower layer focuses exclusively on radar sensor data, employing data fusion techniques to consolidate inputs from multiple radar systems. This serves to reduce visual clutter on the operator interface and enhance the interpretability of target information. The upper layer extends the data fusion process by incorporating sensor inputs from additional sources (ESM, E/O systems, and ADS-B). This enables inter-sensor communication and provides operators with enriched target information for reliable identification processes. Comparative analyses were conducted between the proposed system and C2 systems currently utilized within the Turkish defense infrastructure. Due to confidentiality restrictions, the evaluation was carried out using simulated datasets that closely approximate real-world conditions. The proposed system resulted in a reduction in the standard deviation of operator-displayed data and an increase in data update frequency. These outcomes suggest that the proposed system has the potential to contribute to a more stable, reliable, and responsive operational environment.

1 INTRODUCTION

Air traffic refers to the movements of aircraft in the air during the time between their initial take-off and their return to the airspace for landing. The management of this traffic is conducted through Air Traffic Management (ATM). The primary goal of ATM is to maintain a safe flow of airborne operations while optimizing the use of the airspace's limited capacity. Since the Wright brothers' inaugural flight in 1903, particularly through the technological advancements triggered by World Wars I and II, aviation has undergone rapid development. The number and diversity of flying platforms have surged dramatically [1].

As airspace becomes increasingly congested and the operational environment more intricate, traditional methods of identifying and classifying aircraft are no longer sufficient. The need for accurate, timely, and automated identification has grown, driven by both civilian air safety and military threat detection requirements. Therefore, the modernization of air traffic identification systems has become a priority, particularly with the emergence of new technologies such as radar fusion, electronic warfare detection, and data link-based communication.

The aim of this study is to propose a fast, reliable, and comprehensive system based on a multi-sensor operational framework for the accurate detection, diagnosis, and identification of all airborne vehicles within a defined airspace. The proposed system seeks to leverage recent advancements in technology and the resulting capacity enhancements in air traffic and C2 systems to improve performance in air vehicle recognition and management. Moreover, current airspace monitoring methods are predominantly carried out manually by operators, with limited implementation of automation. This study aims to develop a two-layered decision support system that integrates appropriate algorithms to assist in many of the identification, classification, and traffic separation tasks currently performed by human operators, thereby enabling these processes to be conducted automatically or semi-automatically. The lower layer focuses on intra-sensor fusion by processing and combining data from multiple radars. The upper layer performs inter-sensor fusion by integrating complementary data from ESM, Electro-Optical (E/O), and ADS-B systems. To ensure that fused data belongs to the same target, a dynamic gating distance algorithm is applied at both layers. Comparative evaluations between the proposed system and the current C2 systems (conducted using simulated datasets that closely mimic real-world constraints) have shown a reduction in the standard deviation in data displayed to operators, as well as an increase in update frequency.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the relevant literature is reviewed. Section 3 outlines the methodology used in the study, while section 4 presents the experimental work conducted based on this methodology. Finally, Section 5 discusses the results obtained from these experimental analyses and concludes the study.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Initial efforts in sensor fusion focused solely on radar-based target tracking (see e.g., [2],[3],[4]). However, in dense or ambiguous environments, these methods struggled with track continuity and data association. Multi-sensor data fusion has become increasingly vital in both civilian and military applications due to the limitations of single-sensor systems in dynamic and cluttered environments. Literature provides various approaches to improving target detection, tracking, and identification using various sensor combinations and fusion algorithms in different research areas. For example, [5] introduced fusion algorithms for multi-sensor (radar and infrared) satellite images. [6] conducted a study for maritime transportation. The study focused on obtaining a more accurate maritime situational picture by fusing the data from spatially distributed collaborative sensors with different perspectives. The sensors considered in the study are radars and The Automatic Identification Systems (AIS). In a recent study [7], authors proposed a fusion framework to merge object-list-level data from sensors (cameras, radars, and LiDARs) within smart traffic applications.

Integration of data from different sensor types has also gained importance in air traffic applications. Radar and ESM data integration has been used for joint tracking and identification, leveraging Bayesian methods to distinguish between different types of threats in [8]. This fusion has proven beneficial not only for positional tracking but also for providing additional identification cues like aircraft type and nationality [9]. In [10], the fusion of infrared and radar sensor data is studied. Experiments on a real-life traffic scene demonstrated that combining radar data with infrared data significantly enhances the detection range, reliability, and accuracy of object tracking. In [11], to provide more reliable positional, data from ADS-B sensors and radar systems are fused. In the study, the author concluded that incorporating more than two sensors is necessary to enhance the system's effectiveness.

It should be noted that even though the fusion of radar data with an additional data source has been studied, to the best of the author's knowledge, the fusion of more than 2 different sources in air traffic applications, particularly in military applications, has not been considered in literature. Moreover, many current air traffic and surveillance systems still rely on disjointed sensor data interpretation. Operators must manually correlate information from multiple sources, which increases workload, reduces situational awareness, and introduces delays in threat identification. In high-density or high-risk scenarios, such limitations can lead to operational errors, including misidentification of aircraft.

The literature underscores the growing need for more complex, flexible, and centralized fusion architectures that improve system accuracy and resilience. This study addresses these challenges by proposing a layered sensor fusion architecture for military air traffic systems. The architecture first uses a gating algorithm for initial data association for intra-sensor data (data coming from the several sensors having same type, just radars or just ESM systems). It then incorporates additional sensors (ESM, E/O, ADS-B) in an upper fusion layer which enables real-time, cross-sensor communication. The details of the proposed system are introduced in the next section.

3 SOLUTION METHODOLOGY

Aircraft operating in accordance with published rules and procedures are naturally identified as Friendly, Assumed-Friendly or Neutral, and they monitored as non-threatening air traffic. The aircraft violating the rules or those exhibiting hostile intent during times of crisis or war are typically categorized as Unknown, Suspect, or Hostile. The aim of this study is to generate unified data from different sources that can assist in distinguishing aircraft of different categories, i.e., detection and identification of hostile entities.

Various sensors are used in the detection of an aircraft. The information obtained from these sensors may include both kinematic data (e.g., positional, speed) and non-kinematic data (e.g., nationality, identification). The sensor types considered in this study are radar, ESM (Electronic Support Measures), ADS-B (Automatic Dependent Surveillance–Broadcast), and E/O (Electro-Optical) Systems. The data provided by these sensors are summarized in Table 3.1. Some of the data are numerical in nature (e.g., altitude, speed), others are categorical (e.g., aircraft type, nationality). Although categorical data are not typically used in algorithmic computations, they play a critical role in the identification processes. In certain cases, the presence of a definitive categorical feature may override all other parameters and directly give an identification recommendation.

Table 3.1 – Sensor Data Availability

	Radar	ADS-B	ESM	E/O
Detection	x	x	x	x
Position	x	x	x	x
Altitude	x	x		
Heading	x	x		
Mode 1	x			
Mode 2	x			
Mode 3/A	x	x		
Emission Source			x	
Aircraft Type				x
Nationality		x	x	x
Military/Civilian	x			
Data Quality	x			

At the initial stage, an aircraft detected by sensors is represented as a symbol known as a “plot”. Once an aircraft is detected, a track initiation process begins, and the initiated track is monitored continuously. During tracking, the system must assign an identification to the track based on available data. Tracks initially appear to the operator as pending, and the operator has a limited amount of time to assign an identification. Within this time window, one of six identification categories must be selected: Friendly, Hostile, Neutral, Unknown, Assumed Friendly, or Suspect.

This process is essential not only for preventing collisions and ensuring safe air traffic during peacetime, but also for rapidly enabling the survival and defensive capabilities of friendly combat aircraft during wartime. Particularly in times of war, if friendly aircraft cannot survive, their capabilities such as precision weapons and rapid targeting become meaningless. The responses and defensive measures taken against hostile or suspected aircraft differ significantly from those directed at aircraft identified as friendly or neutral, which are considered non-threatening. Misidentifying a genuinely friendly aircraft as hostile and engaging can even trigger the outbreak of a conflict. For this reason, completing the identification process accurately is of critical importance.

3.1 Current System

In the current system, only aircraft detected via radar are transmitted to C2 centers for identification purposes. C2 centers incorporate detected tracks into their monitoring areas and are responsible for assigning identifications to those tracks. To fuse the data of the same target obtained with different radars, a quality measure is used and only the data of radar with the highest quality is used and others are ignored.

In this study, the aim is to utilize an effective fusion of radar data without ignoring any and subsequently the fusion of data obtained from different types of sensors for the purpose of identifying aerial targets. Naturally, due to legal and procedural considerations, the final responsibility for identification remains with the operator. Thus, the output produced by this study will serve as recommendations rather than definitive decisions. Given the high density of airspace and the potential for human error, even advisory outputs provided by decision support systems can be highly beneficial. For instance, in current practice, unidentified aircraft often necessitate military scramble operations to determine their identity. These actions not only incur significant operational costs but can also lead to diplomatic repercussions. In some unfortunate cases, misidentification has even led to the downing of friendly or civilian aircraft. Based on these considerations, this study emphasizes the utility of automatic identification processes.

3.2 Proposed System

The methodology in this study consists of two main stages. In the first stage, data from similar sources (e.g., multiple radars) are associated, merged, and reduced to a single, unified data point. In

the second stage, previously fused data from different sources (e.g., ESM, ADS-B) are combined to produce a final, fused, and unique dataset. As illustrated in Figure 3.1, the first layer represents raw data from each sensor (e.g., Radar A and B; ESM C, D, and E), the middle layer contains fused and unified data from similar sources, and the last layer shows the integration of unified data from different sensor types.

Figure 3.1 – Fused Unique Data Structure (Multiline, Larger Fonts)

At the first layer, radar plot data from different sources are processed using a gating distance–based algorithm commonly employed in the literature to determine which plots correspond to the same target. Plot data deemed to belong to the same target are then merged, resulting in a single, fused radar data point for that target. This consolidated data point is referred to as a "super plot."

It is assumed that a similar fusion process is conducted among homogeneous sensors such as ESM, ADS-B, and electro-optical (E/O) systems, producing analogous "super plots." Subsequently, these super plots—presumed to belong to the same target—are analyzed and fused once more, generating a single, unified dataset. This final dataset serves as the input for the identification process.

In real-world systems, algorithms that produce super plots by incorporating data from multiple radars using gating distance are generally not employed. Instead, one radar is typically selected based on predefined quality metrics, and data from the remaining radars are disregarded. Furthermore, in practical scenarios, data from heterogeneous sensors are typically combined manually by human operators to determine whether they correspond to the same target. There are currently no fully integrated systems that automatically store, analyze, fuse, and classify such data. [12] emphasized the necessity of centralizing and monitoring data collected from multiple sensor systems.

This study utilizes the kinematic data (position, speed, etc.) from each radar proportionally to their respective quality scores, ensuring that no radar is excluded at the first layer. For categorical data, if values are consistent across radars, they are merged into a single value. In the case of inconsistencies, all options are presented, and the final decision is deferred to the operator. Like the radar-based process, data from different types of sensors in the next layer are also subjected to a gating distance algorithm to assess whether they refer to the same target. Kinematic data from these sensors are then utilized in proportion to reliability coefficients determined via the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) [13], again ensuring that no data are discarded and minimizing potential data loss. For categorical variables, the same approach as in the first layer is followed: consistent values are merged, while conflicting values are presented to the operator for final judgment.

3.1.1 Intra-Sensor Data Fusion

In this section, we detail the process of fusing data originating from sensors of the same type. Without loss of generality, the procedure is illustrated using radar data, although the same principles apply to other sensors such as ESM, E/O, and ADS-B. Radars are strategically deployed to maximize coverage, particularly at low altitudes. However, at higher altitudes, their detection zones may overlap depending on the distance between installations. As a result, it is possible to receive multiple radar

plots for the same target. To perform accurate data fusion, it is essential to ensure that the plots being combined indeed belong to the same target.

In conventional systems, when multiple radars detect what is assumed to be the same target, the corresponding plots are evaluated based on a quality score (typically derived from the radar's update frequency over a given time interval). Only the data from the radar with the highest quality is used for tracking, while other inputs are disregarded. This practice can lead to data loss and positional inaccuracies. To address these limitations, this study proposes a more robust approach. When multiple radars detect the same target, their positional data should be merged. This technique fuses position information into a single location estimate, weighted proportionally to each radar's quality coefficient. However, before performing this fusion, it is critical to verify that the data being combined refers to the same target.

To support this verification, a Gating Distance algorithm, as used in many previous studies (e.g., [8]), is applied. Gating distance represents the estimated range within which a plot is expected to appear during the next radar update and is calculated by multiplying the target's speed by the update interval. When updates from multiple radars are available, the gating distance is independently calculated for each radar's most recent plot. Circular regions, centered on each plot with a radius equal to the calculated gating distance, are drawn. If these circles intersect, the corresponding plots are assumed to represent the same target. Once this determination is made, plot data from radars are fused to obtain super plot. In Figure 3.2, this process is summarized. Two data points are represented with crosses, each surrounded by its own gating circle. The circles intersect (shown as the shaded region) implying that the data points belong to the same target. The data are then fused, and the resulting super plot is illustrated as a cloud surrounding the corresponding cross.

Figure 3.2 – Gating Distance and Super Plot

The position of the super plot is calculated using the linear combination method, which aggregates the most recent location data from all contributing radars proportional to their qualities. For other continuous variables such as altitude and heading, weighted averages are computed using the radar quality scores. The result is a coherent, singular dataset representing the target. Categorical data (e.g., aircraft type) is handled differently. If identical values are reported across sources, a single unified value is included in the super plot. If differences are found, all distinct values are retained and presented, ensuring no information is lost. Each time a new radar update is received, the gating distance is recalculated. If the new plot lies within the intersection area of existing gating circles, the super plot is updated accordingly.

In summary, radar plots initially represented by separate symbols are assessed using gating distance to determine target identity. Once confirmed as belonging to the same target, they are merged into a single super plot that consolidates data from all relevant sources proportional to their quality scores. Unlike conventional systems that rely exclusively on the highest-quality radar input and ignore potential inconsistencies, the proposed method incorporates data from all radars. By also retaining all categorical discrepancies, the approach enhances operator awareness and prevents critical data loss.

As described in fusion of radar data, the same procedures can also be implemented for ESM, E/O, and ADS-B sensors. That is, by applying a gating distance algorithm, super plots can be generated using data assumed to belong to the same target.

3.1.2 Multi-Sensor Data Fusion

As mentioned before, fused data from different sensor sources is integrated again at a higher layer. Just as in the radar sub-layer, gating distances calculated from the super plot data of different sources can be used to determine whether data from different sensors belong to the same target.

In Figure 3.3, four different sensor sources and their gating circles are represented with different colors. The radar, shown in green, has a 10-second update interval; the ESM source, shown in blue, updates every 6 seconds; the electro-optical (E/O) sensor, shown in orange, every 3 seconds; and the ADS-B sensor, shown in purple, updates every 2 seconds. Due to the varying update intervals, gating distances will differ even if the speed values are nearly identical. Considering that this discrepancy may hinder correct data association, a fixed update interval may be adopted for gating distance calculations across all sensors. In this study, the radar's update interval of 10 seconds (the highest value among all) is selected as a reference value.

Figure 3.3 – Gating Distance with Different Sensor Sources

With a fixed 10-second interval for all sensors, the gating circles on the latest data are found as illustrated in Figure 3.3. As the gating circles of different sensors intersect the data points are considered to belong to the same target and they need to be unified. During this unification process, the position data will be fused using a linear combination method like the radar sub-layer. However, unlike the radar layer, the weights for this combination are not derived from sensor-reported quality scores but are instead determined using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). This is because only radar sensors provide quality metrics for their data, whereas other sensors do not. Therefore, applying AHP-derived weights is considered more suitable for calculating the fused position.

The AHP questionnaire was completed by a group of four experts, including one HAVELSAN employee and three retired members of the Turkish Armed Forces (TSK). The purpose of the survey was to determine the relative weights of four sensors for their numerical data outputs (e.g., position, heading). 8 questions were asked to make pairwise comparisons of sensors. Figure 3.4 shows an example from the questionnaire which compares radar and ESM data. The main levels 1, 3, 5, 7, and 9 mean equal, slightly better, better, much better, and significantly better, respectively. Intermediate levels 2, 4, 6, and 8 are used to express nuances between the main levels.

Figure 3.4 – A Question from the AHP Questionnaire

Computed weights were then used during the data fusion process to calculate the super track's position and associated numerical values. According to the results of the AHP method, the radar was identified as the most reliable sensor for numerical data, followed by ADS-B, ESM and E/O sensors. This ranking is reliable because the consistency ratio of 0.088 is below the 0.1 threshold. The ranking

aligns with expectations as sensors other than radar are primarily used to provide supplementary information about targets (e.g., aircraft type, nationality) rather than kinematic measurements. Due to confidentiality, the exact weights derived from the AHP process cannot be disclosed; therefore, simulated weights consistent with the identified ranking are used in this study.

The same approach used in the radar layer can be applied to all other non-position data. Numerical data (e.g., altitude, heading) will be fused using a weighted average based on AHP-derived weights. For categorical data, if consistent across sources, a single value will be retained. If discrepancies occur, all values will be presented to avoid information loss. If data is missing, no processing will be done, and the information will be passed up to the next layer as is.

4 COMPUTATIONAL EXPERIMENTS

4.1 Radar Data Fusion (Lower Level)

In this part, plot data of 40 updates obtained from two different long-range air defense radars operating in real-world conditions is utilized. The plot data identified as belonging to the same target are merged using the methodology described in Section 3 and are used to construct super plots.

Figure 4.1 Current System

Figure 4.2 Current vs. Proposed System

In Figure 4.1, raw data (time, latitude, and longitude) of two radars (orange and purple points) and the current system's track output (green line) are represented for only 4 plots (updates). The operator only sees updates when the highest-quality data arrives. During the first two updates represented by the green line, only time updates are displayed, no position updates. In the third and fourth, since the data received was of higher quality both time and position updates were shown. As can be seen from the graph, although four updates in total were received, the operator was only presented with two updates on their screen due to the filtering mechanism of the current system.

Figure 4.2 compares the output of the current system and the proposed gating algorithm. The updates visible to the operator (green line) are compared with the results of the proposed algorithm (red line). As shown in the graph, the current system performs only time updates for the first two inputs without updating the position. During this period, the proposed algorithm utilizes data from both radars proportionally based on their quality scores, enabling more frequent and dynamic updates for the operator. Importantly, the proposed method (red line) does not repeat the same position value across updates. Instead, it recalculates and updates the target's position with each new input. Since the linear combination method is used in these calculations, the resulting position shifts are significantly smaller than those in the current system. This is evident in the green line representing

the operator's current system, the position change between the second and third updates is much larger than the position shifts between consecutive gating updates. Thus, the proposed method not only provides more frequent updates but also reduces the variability between position estimates. It should be noted that all fusion computations are completed in less than one second, and the resulting super plot is displayed to the operator at the following second after the last data update.

Figure 4.3 Current vs. Proposed System Applied to All Data

All the radar data used in this study is visualized in Figure 4.3. For clarity, a zoomed-in view has been included on the right side of the figure. As seen in the graph, the red trajectory representing the proposed algorithm follows a more stable path compared to the green trajectory of the current system. Using the X and Y coordinates derived from the graphs, the sample standard deviations for both methods are calculated. The standard deviations for both the X and Y coordinates are lower in the proposed method when all data points are considered. Specifically, the standard deviation of the X coordinates in the current system was calculated as 0.012298472, while the proposed algorithm produced a reduced standard deviation of 0.007400165. For the Y coordinates, the standard deviation under the current system is 0.220183463, whereas the proposed algorithm achieved a lower value of 0.177653683. When comparing the number of non-updated entries across the two systems, the current system failed to update 3 data points, while the proposed method successfully updated all data.

The proposed system was shown to reduce variability. To determine whether this difference was statistically significant, an F-test was conducted at a 90% confidence level separately to the X and Y coordinate values. For the X coordinate, the test statistic was found to be 2.76, while the critical value was 1.83. This indicates that the variance in the X coordinate differs significantly between the current system and the proposed method. For the Y coordinate, the test statistic was 1.53, while the critical value remained 1.83 and the null hypothesis could not be rejected for the Y coordinate. Since the null hypothesis was rejected for one of the coordinate dimensions, it can be concluded that the proposed system provides improved positional stability.

4.2 Multi-Sensor Data Fusion (Higher Level)

Some of the data types presented in Table 3.1 are military data and classified in nature; therefore, due to the inaccessibility of real data, simulated data will be used throughout the remainder of the study. In Figure 4.4, an example of the output of our decision support system is provided. In the first data row, the plots received from E/O and ESM sensors were processed through the gating algorithm and were determined to belong to the same target. It is observed that these two sensors do

not provide values for speed, altitude, heading, or transponder mode information. Therefore, the corresponding cells are marked as 0 or none. The key point in this row is the nationality field. The E/O and ESM sensors provided conflicting nationality information for the target. Consequently, both values are presented in the table, leaving the final decision to the operator.

In the third data row of Figure 4.4, a super plot from the radar layer (fused data of radar 53 and 54), along with data from both the ADS-B and ESM sensors, were processed through the gating algorithm. Both radar and ADS-B provided speed, altitude, and heading data. Accordingly, the values for these parameters were calculated using the weights determined by the AHP for these two sensors. Since the aircraft type parameter was provided exclusively by the ESM sensor, the value was taken directly from it. For the nationality field, both ADS-B and ESM provided input, but their values differed. As a result, both values are displayed, leaving the operator to make the final decision. Similarly, for the Mode 3/A code, two radars and the ADS-B sensor reported different values. All three values are shown in the output, and again the final decision is left to the operator. For the position field, the fused coordinate was calculated using the AHP-derived weights for all contributing sensors.

Sensör	Zaman	Konum	Hız	Irtifa	Yön	Tip	Milliyet	M1	M2	M3A	Askeri/Sivil
eo/esm	217.485	(38.32118, 27.02558)	0	0	0	Rafale	Orta Afrika/Endonezya	None	None	None	Askeri
53/54	218.85	(38.32312, 26.7723)	931	9255	231	None	None	11	2021	2384/2109	Askeri
53/54/adbs/esm	223.741	(38.31901, 26.79255)	737	8915	202	Rafale	Alman/Endonezya	11	2021	2384/2589/2356	Askeri

Figure 4.4 Output of Decision Support System for Multi-Sensor Fusion

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a comprehensive system with a multi-sensor framework is proposed to ensure the accurate identification and classification of various types and numbers of aircraft in air traffic. A two-layer approach based on gating algorithm is developed. In the current systems used in C2 centers, only radars are employed as a detection sensor, and data from other sensors are manually informed to the operator. Furthermore, there is no existing modern system capable of integrating data from multiple radars without loss. The current system relies solely on the radar with higher-quality data and disregards other radars entirely. Consequently, no new update is applied to a track until better-quality data arrives. This mechanism only functions meaningfully if higher-quality data are consistently available. However, when data quality degrades, prolonged update gaps or complete disregard of available information can lead to track loss or inaccurate assessments.

To address current problems, the lower layer of the proposed system does not discard data from multiple radars, even when quality is reduced. Instead, all radar outputs are utilized in proportion to their reported quality scores. For data believed to belong to the same target, the gating algorithm reduces them to a single track. The fused position is then calculated using a linear combination method that incorporates radar quality values. Similarly, other numerical radar data such as heading and altitude are also included in the fusion process without omitting the associated quality values. This lower-layer fusion simplifies the operator's display by reducing visual clutter and ensures more balanced data delivery. The gating algorithm was executed using real data from two different radars. The outputs were examined both for a small sample case and the entire dataset. The results showed that the proposed method significantly reduced the standard deviation for both X and Y coordinates compared to the current system. Since real-world radar data were used, the findings suggest that the proposed approach offers practical benefits for operational environments.

Moreover, the current system lacks integration with non-radar sensors, which leads to the absence of critical information such as aircraft type or nationality, both of which are important for classification and decision-making. To resolve this, the upper layer of the proposed system replicates the gating process of lower layer, now incorporating data from ESM, E/O, and ADS-B sensors in addition to radar. The upper layer aims to enable real-time interaction between sensors, allowing them

to share information and provide more comprehensive situational awareness that supports the operator in the identification process. Since non-radar sensors do not provide data quality metrics, an AHP survey involving four criteria (one for each sensor) was conducted with experts. The resulting weights were used in the data fusion process for numerical fields. Analysis of the consistent AHP results indicated that radar is the most reliable sensor for positional and numerical data, followed by ADS-B, E/O and ESM sensors.

The proposed architecture is developed for air defense domain. Expanding the architecture to include maritime and ground surveillance domains, improving operator interfaces, and exploring dynamic sensor weighting strategies based on real-time performance metrics represent promising research directions.

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